

CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING AND PRIVACY-PRESERVING TECHNOLOGIES FOR 6G

D1.4 PROJECT REVIEW REPORT (V1)

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document provides an overview of the activities in the first reporting period of the project (M1-M18, January 2023 – June 2024). The document also summarizes the project impact targets and current status as well as the open science approach of the project. Essentially this document corresponds to an early version of the Part B Technical report of the Periodic report that will be submitted in August 2024.

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